

**SEXUAL COMMUNICATION TECHNIQUES AS EXPRESSED BY
COLLEGES OF EDUCATION STAFF IN KWARA STATE**

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Abstract

This study examined sexual communication techniques among Colleges of Education in Kwara State. The research design adopted for this study was a descriptive survey. The population for this study comprised the entire staff (academic and non-academic) of all the Colleges of Education in Kwara State. A researcher self-developed questionnaire was designed. The questionnaire was validated using face and content validity to determine the extent to which the statements items of the questionnaire corresponded with the objectives of this study. The reliability of the instrument was established by employing split-half reliability method. Cronbachs alpha reliability statistics was used and coefficient of 0.735 was obtained. The t-test and ANOVA were used to test hypotheses one and two postulated respectively. One of the findings revealed that there was a significant difference in the sexual communication techniques of male and female which favoured female staff. It also revealed that there was a significant difference in the sexual commendation techniques on the basis of ethnicity. It favored the Yorubas. It was concluded that sexual communication and good sexual behaviours are crucial elements in healthy relationship. One of the recommendations suggested that there is the need for marital adjustment between husband and wife. There must be mutual respect, validation of feeling, active listening and willingness to compromise and negotiate between couples.

Introduction

Communication is defined as the process by which meaning is exchanged between individuals through a common system of symbols, signs or behaviour. It involves the transmission of message from sender to a receiver. Communication is considered a process because it is an activity an exchange of a set of product (Pearson, Nelson & Harter, 2003).

Ijeoma (1991) also defined communication as a process of transferring information from one entity to another. It is commonly defined as the imparting or exchange of thoughts, opinions or information by speech, writing or signs. Hathway (1998) supported Ijeoma and stated that communication is a process whereby information is enclosed in a package, channeled and imported by a sender to a receiver and it is given via some medium. The receiver then decodes the message and gives the sender a feedback.

There are two major forms of communication: (i) verbal communication which involves not just the specific words used but also the vocal tone and the speed with which we talk; Verbal communication involves everything we, as a listener, hear when talking to another person or persons; (ii) Non-verbal communication on the other hand, involves everything that the listeners or receivers see during conversation. This could be in the form of body language, facial expressions, nervousness, physical grooming, personal mannerisms and other idiosyncrasies communication. It is the exchange of information without the use of words.

However, Akinade (1997) asserted that communication between spouses could be verbal and non-verbal and that both should understand and appreciate this. Kolo (1993) also observed that crucial element in a healthy relationship is where communication is effective and it helps in moulding well desired behaviours which lead to happy relationship.

Bello (2009) supported Kolo (1990) and stated that communication is the mortar that holds a relationship together. If it breaks down, the relationship will crumble. He further explained that true communication involves respect for the other person. Kolo (1993) agreed that respect allows couples to accept one another's point of view whole-heartedly. He further explained that couples should consider and value their spouse's perspectives and suggestions as well as allowing your partner know that you respect and has value for him or her.

Sexual Communication Techniques

Egan (1997) referred to sexual communication as the range of expressive behaviours we find in established couples, both dating and married that enables them to achieve satisfying sexual relationships. Wikipedia (2010) defined communication style or techniques as the way one verbally and para-verbally interacts to signal, Rich and Copans (1998) stressed that couples use different terms to describe aspects of their sexual experience. For example, when speaking to each other, men seem to communicate frequently about a wide range of sexual experience. They tend to use words that are referred to as power slang (Sanders and Robinson 1979; Simkins and Rinck, 1982).

Gender and Sexual Communication

The role of men on many cultures especially in Nigeria is sexual initiator and the role of women as sexual “gatekeeper”, women sometimes adopt a communication strategy of saying “No” when they are, in fact, willing to engage in sexual activity. Muchlenhard & Hollabough (1988); Muchlenhard and Mc Coy (1991) refer to this practice as “token resistance” and suggest that it may be employed by women to avoid appearing 'easy' or promiscuous. It can sometimes be confused with a sincere expression of intent not to engage in sexual intercourse. When a woman says “no” to sex and means it, but a man interprets it as token resistance and continues to pursue sexual activity, negotiation is no longer collaborative but coercive (Krahe, Scheinberger-Olwig & Kolpin, 2000). In these instances, his continued pursuit becomes sexual intimidation and aggression, it may even lead to rape. (Abbey, 1991). By contrast, females discuss sex less often. These differences in vocabularies for talking about sex may influence early-pattern of sexual talk. Similarly, Simkins and Rinck (1982) asserted that when men use sexual terms, which may sound rough, demeaning, or non-romantic to women: when women use sexual terms they may sound too cute silly or clinical. Scholars often termed these slangs as couple's unique personal idioms, especially those idioms for genitalia sexual rituals and routines (Bardwell, 1997; Gore, 1987). This study therefore, examined attitude of staff of Colleges of Education in Kwara State on sexual communication techniques.

Statement of the Problem

Series of research work have been carried out on sexual communication. For instance, Simkins and Rinck (1982) wrote on male and female sexual vocabulary in different interpersonal contexts. George (1997) studied sexual behaviour and

communication among adults, Kolo (1993) researched on a survey of pleasant and unpleasant communication among married couples: Some implications for marital dysfunctions. Lina (2010) wrote on four communication styles of married couple. Lastly, Terry (2010) examined the role of foreplay in sexual union. In view of the loci of most researchers cited so far, there are no enough studies on sexual techniques among educational and social institutions in Nigeria. Therefore, this study would examined sexual communication techniques in tertiary institutions in Kwara State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised based on the objectives of the study:

- What are the sexual communication techniques adopted by the staff of Colleges of Education in Kwara Tate?
- Is there any difference in the sexual communication techniques of male and female staff of Colleges of Education in Kwara State?
- Is there any difference in the sexual communication techniques of staff of Colleges of Education of Kwara State on the basis of ethnicity?

Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were postulated to assist the study achieve the stated objectives:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the sexual communication techniques of male and female staff of Colleges of Education in Kwara State.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the sexual communication techniques of staff of Colleges of Education in Kwara State on the basis of Ethnicity.

METHODOLOGY

This section deals with the general procedures that were employed in carrying out this study.

Research Design

The research design adopted for this study was the descriptive survey. Donna (1998) explains that descriptive research gives a picture of a situation or a population as it exists. It allows assessment of opinions that are held and gives a vivid description of what it is in the area of study. The rationale for using descriptive research method

staff of tertiary institutions on sexual communication and sexual habits.

Population, Sample and Sampling Techniques

The populations for this study comprised of the entire staff (academic and non-academic) of all the Colleges of Education in Kwara State. As at the time of this report there are seven Colleges of Education. Four Colleges of Education were randomly selected. In each of the institution selected, 50 and 100 were sampled from academic and non-academic staff respectively. Selections were based on random selection irrespective of their Department. Hence, 600 staff were used as sample size.

Research Instrument

The instrument used for this study was researcher self developed questionnaire. It is titled "Attitude of staff of Colleges of Education on Sexual Communication Techniques Questionnaire (ASCESCT)". This type of instrument was chosen because it is an effective way of collecting information from a large number of respondents within a short period (Donna, 1998). The questionnaire used was divided into 2 sections. Section A contained items on the personal characteristics of the respondents such as gender, religion, and ethnic group. Section B consisted of 20 items which addressed sexual communication techniques. Responses to these items were scored on 4-point Likert Type Scale i.e. Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree and Strongly Disagree.

Validity of the Instrument

The validity of the instrument was obtained using face and content validity approach. This approach was used to determine the extent to which the content (items) of the questionnaire corresponds with the objectives of this study. To ascertain the validity of this questionnaire, two experts in Educational Research, Measurement and Evaluation at University of Ilorin and Kwara State College of Education, Ilorin were given. This is to assess the items/statements in questionnaire whether they tallied with the objectives, research questions and research hypotheses. During this process, some items considered duplicated and ambiguous were deleted while some others were reconstructed.

Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability of the instrument was established by employing split-half reliability method. To do this, the questionnaire was administered to 5 and 10 academics and non-academics staff in a college different from those sampled college

for this study who did not form part of the final respondents of this study. Responses to these statements were divided into half; all the odd and even responses were scored and coded on statistical coding sheets separately. The set of data were subjected to Cronbach's Alpha reliability statistics and correlation coefficient of 0.735 was obtained.

Procedure for Data Collection

The researcher administered the questionnaire to the respondents in all the 4 sampled Colleges of Education in Kwara State. The questionnaire was distributed and retrieved within 2 weeks. In some of the institutions visited, questionnaire was completed immediately and returned to the researcher. However, the entire questionnaires administered were returned.

Method of Data Analysis

Frequency counts and percentage were used to describe demographic characteristics of the respondents. Three research questions were raised. A research question was answered with the use of descriptive statistics (mean and Standard deviation). Other two research questions have corresponding hypotheses and they were tested with inferential statistics. Hypothesis one was tested with independent t-test while hypothesis two was tested with analysis of Variance (ANOVA), at level of significance 0.05.

RESULTS

This section deals with collation, analysis and interpretation of data collected as illustrated below. The questionnaire was scored in accordance with the format of each section. Section A which consisted of personal characteristics of the respondents was analyzed using simple percentage. Section B which consisted of items on the attitude of staff of colleges Education in Kwara State on sexual communication techniques were coded 4 = Strongly Agree; 3 = Agree; 2 = Strongly Disagree; and 1 = Disagree on statistical coding sheets.

Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Frequency counts and percentage were used to describe the personal characteristics of the respondents in Ilorin metropolis as shown below:

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Table 1: Distribution of Respondents on the Basis of Gender

Variables	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	293	48.83
	Female	307	57.17
	Total	600	100.0
Ethnicity	Yoruba	299	46.83
	Hausa	59	9.83
	Igbo	16	2.67
	Nupe	149	24.83
	Bokobaru	77	12.83
	Total	600	100.0

Source: Author's Field-work 2012

Table 1 above shows that out of 600 academics and non-academics staff that were sampled, 293 (48.83%) were males, while 307 (57.17%) were females. It also shows that 299 (49.83%) were from Yoruba speaking community, 59 (9.83%) were Hausas, 16 (2.67%) were Igbos, 149 (24.83%) were from Nupe Community while the rest 77 (12.83%) were from Bokobaru ethnic speaking community.

Answering of Research Questions

The only research question for this study was answered with the use of descriptive statistics (mean).

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What are the sexual Communication techniques adopted by staff of Colleges of Education in Kwara State?*

In order to answer this question, responses of the staff of Colleges of Education on sexual communication techniques were collated and subjected to descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation). The mean is ranked as illustrated below:

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Table2: Sexual Communication Techniques adopted by Staff of Colleges of Education in Kwara State?

Statements	Mean	Rank
As far as I am concerned:		
I'm not afraid to stand up for myself on sexual issues	3.59	1 st
It is easy for me to tell my partner what I need him/her to do to satisfy me sexually	3.21	2 nd
Even when I'm really in the mood to have sex, I prefer to wait to let my partner initiate sex	3.02	3 rd
If anything about our sex life is bothering my partner, I prefer to hear about it even if it causes me distress	2.86	4 th
I feel completely comfortable with my sexuality	2.74	5 th
If I want to have sex, I'm more likely to "hint" around that I'm interested instead of just asking outright.	2.69	6 th
Generally, I tend to be inhibited about having sex	2.66	7 th
If I am dissatisfied with something about our sex life, I don't hesitate to tell my people	2.57	8 th
Generally, I tend to be inhibited talking about sex	2.46	9 th
If my partner is unhappy with our sex life, I would rather not know about it	2.37	10 th
If we're having problems with sex, I tend to let them build up for a long time before I say anything	2.36	11 th
I often pretend to be more interested in sex than I really am, in order to please or avoid hurting my spouse	2.35	12 th
I find it difficult telling my partner if something about his/her sexual performance is bothering me	1.90	13 th
If I don't actually have an orgasm during intercourse, but I usually pretend to have one	1.84	14 th

Table 2 shows that out of 14 statements prepared that addressed sexual communication techniques, statement which stated that "I am not afraid to stand up for myself on sexual issue" ranked first with mean of 3.59. Statement which stated that "It is easy for me to tell my partner what I need him/her to do to satisfy me sexually" ranked second with mean of 3.21. Statement which stated that "Even when I'm really in the mood to have sex, I prefer to wait to let my partner initiate sex" ranked third with mean of 3.02. Responses to other items had mean lower than 3.02.

Hypotheses Testing

In the course of this study, 2 hypotheses were postulated. Hypothesis 1 was tested with the use of independent t-test while hypothesis 2 was tested with the use of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) at level of significance 0-05.

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H₀: *There is no significant difference in the sexual communication techniques of male and female staff of Colleges of Education in Kwara State.*

In order to test this hypothesis, responses of the staff of Colleges of Education in Kwara State to sexual communication techniques were collated on the basis of gender. The data was then subjected to t-test statistical techniques as shown below

Table 3: The t-test Analysis Showing Difference in the Sexual Communication Techniques of Staff of Colleges of Education in Kwara State on the basis of Gender.

Gender	No	Mean	Std.	Df	Cal r-value	Critical r-value
Male	293	23.90	5.50	598	27.146*	.196
Female	307	46.99	7.09			

* = Significant, $p < 0.05$

Table 3 above shows that the calculated t-value is 27.146 while the critical r-value is .196 with 598 degree of freedom and at level of significance 0.05. Since the calculated t-value is greater than the critical t-value, hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis accepted. That is, there is a significant difference in the sexual communication techniques of male and female of staff of Colleges of Education in Kwara State. This is in favour of female with mean of 46.99 greater than the mean (23.90) of male staff.

H₀: *There is no significant difference in the sexual Communication techniques of staff of Colleges of Education in Kwara State on the basis of ethnicity.*

In order to test this hypothesis, responses of staff of Colleges of Education in Kwara State to items on sexual communication techniques were collated on the basis of ethnic groups. The set of data was subjected to Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and the output reveals as shown in the table below.

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Table 4: ANOVA Analysis showing Differences in the sexual Communication Techniques of staff of Colleges of Education in Kwara State. on the Basis of Ethnicity.

	SS	df	Mean	Cal F-Value	Crit F-Value
Between groups	32080.282	4	8020.070	278.252*	2.60
Within groups	6341.167	595	28.823		
Total	38421.449	599			

*=Significant, $p < 0.05$

Table 4 shows that the calculated F-ratio is 278.252 while the critical F-ratio is 2.60 with 4 and 594 degrees of freedom and at level of significance 0.05. Since the calculated F-ratio is greater than the critical F-ratio, the hypothesis is rejected while the alternative hypothesis accepted. That is, there is a significant difference in the sexual communication techniques of married adults on the basis of ethnic groups. To ascertain where the significant difference lies, Duncan Multiple Range Test was carried out and the output revealed as shown in table 4

Table 5: Duncan Multiple Range Test Showing Significant Differences among Ethnic Groups

Ethnicity	No	Subset for alpha = 0.05			
		1	2	3	4
Yoruba	299	39			
Hausa	59		42.000		
Igbo	16			47.14	
Nupe	149				54.43
Bokobaru	77	1.000	.135	1.000	1.000

The significant difference lies with Yoruba in subset 1 followed by Hausa and Igbo in subset 2. Nupe is found in subset 3 while Bokobaru is in subset 4.

Summary of the findings

Based on the analysis and interpretation of data collected, the following findings are obtained:

1. There is a significant difference in the sexual communication techniques of male and female staff of Colleges of Education in Kwara State. It is in favour

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of female staff of Colleges of Education in Kwara State.

2. There is a significant difference in the sexual communication techniques of staff of Colleges of Education in Kwara State on the basis of ethnicity and it favours Yorubas.

Discussion

Discussion of findings was based on the analysis, interpretation and findings obtained in this study. The first finding revealed that a significant difference existed between male and female staff of Colleges of Education in Kwara State on the sexual communication techniques. This finding is in line with Castrovazquez and Kishi (2002) who observed that slangs are frequently used by men to communicate about sex to establish sexual reputation. By contrast, female discuss sexless often in some gender groups and seems to prefer clinical and or cute sexual slangs (Sanders & Robinson, 1976; Simkins & Rincks 1982).

The second finding revealed that a significant difference in the sexual communication techniques of staff of Colleges of Education in Kwara State on the basis of ethnic background. This finding is in agreement with Lapage and Tabouret-keller (1985) observed that every cultural group has behavioural patterns. Gagon and Simon, (2005) observed that all societies restricted sexual communication through explicitly and implicit social rules. These dynamics exists within a structured set of behavioural guidelines that create cultural norms for how sex and sexuality can be expressed. Bell and Gordon (1972), identify that cultural factor created variation in psychological, social and physical responses to human sexuality.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it could be concluded that sexual communication and good sexual behaviours are crucial elements in healthy relationship between staff of Colleges of Education in Kwara State. This is because it is the ingredient in any relationship between couples. It was found that males have wider range of sexual experiences. This is attributed to their level of interaction with powerful slangs. The result of the findings also revealed that language spoken which is a form of culture allowed individual to project their identity and shape it according to the behaviour patterns of the group with which they wish to identify. The finding is in favour of Yoruba socio-cultural group of married civil servants in Ilorin metropolis.

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Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of this study, the following recommendations are put forward:

1. There is also the need for marital adjustment between husband and wife. Marital adjustment denotes a relatively harmonious relationship within and between individuals. This will bring mutual satisfaction to one spouse and compatibility of individual traits.
2. There must be mutual respect, validation of feelings, active listening, willingness to compromise and negotiate between couples
3. Couples should avoid making their partners feel invisible when one spouse feels invisible, it often leads to a communication breakdown which may later lead to divorce.
4. When in doubt or when conflict arises between couples, they should seek help from marital therapist or counselor because it can help to unravel a couple's problems and get them reframe and readjust how they communicate and behave.
5. There is need for the couples to have empathic understanding of each other; this may promote effective interpersonal relationship

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